

INTELLIGENT COLLEGE ENQUIRY CHATBOT USING NLP FOR ENHANCED STUDENT INTERACTION

Dr.A. Karunamurthy

Associate Professor, Department of computer Applications,
Sri Manakula Vinayagar Engineering College (Autonomous), Puducherry 605008, India

R. Ramakrishnan

Associate Professor, Department of computer Applications,
Sri Manakula Vinayagar Engineering College (Autonomous), Puducherry 605008, India

S.Jothsana

Post Graduate student, Department of computer Applications,
Sri Manakula Vinayagar Engineering College (Autonomous), Puducherry 605008, India

M.Roshni

Post Graduate student, Department of computer Applications,
Sri Manakula Vinayagar Engineering College (Autonomous), Puducherry 605008, India

*Corresponding author's email address: jothsiva2002@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This project aims to develop a College Enquiry Chatbot that leverages Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to address queries posted by students, such as college details, course-related questions, location, fee structure, and more. The chatbot is a web application designed to analyze and comprehend user messages using machine learning algorithms integrated with NLP for enhanced query understanding and response accuracy. Users can interact with the system by simply typing their queries into the chatbot, which provides precise and contextually relevant answers. The chatbot eliminates the need for students to visit the college in person for inquiries. Additionally, users can provide feedback or suggestions through a dedicated suggestion box. The system features an engaging Graphical User Interface (GUI), simulating an interaction akin to conversing with a real person. The project employs HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for the frontend and Python for the backend, with NLP models enabling robust question analysis and response generation.

By automating the information-seeking process, this system not only streamlines communication but also enhances accessibility and efficiency for students. Implementing the College Enquiry Chatbot can significantly improve prospective student engagement and satisfaction.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing (NLP), Chatbot, Intent Recognition, Entity Extraction, Machine Learning, Query Classification, Response Generation

Cite this Article: A.Karunamurthy, R. Ramakrishnan, S.Jothsana and M.Roshni, Intelligent College Enquiry Chatbot Using NLP For Enhanced Student Interaction, *Journal of Advanced Research Engineering and Technology (JARET)*, 3(2), 2024, pp. 30-37

<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/JARET?Volume=3&Issue=2>

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, educational institutions are increasingly adopting technology to improve communication and operational efficiency. One such innovation is the use of chatbots—artificial intelligence-powered tools designed to interact with users through natural language. These systems have demonstrated immense potential in various domains, including education, where they serve as virtual assistants capable of answering inquiries, guiding students, and streamlining administrative processes. Students and prospective applicants often face challenges in obtaining timely and accurate information about colleges, including course offerings, fee structures, and campus details. Traditional methods like in-person visits or static web pages can be time-consuming and inconvenient. To address these issues, intelligent chatbots powered by Natural Language Processing (NLP) provide a scalable, interactive, and efficient alternative.

The proposed College Enquiry Chatbot leverages NLP and machine learning to understand and respond to user queries with contextual accuracy. This system enhances accessibility by allowing users to interact through a web-based interface, eliminating the need for physical visits. Additionally, features such as user feedback mechanisms ensure continuous improvement of the chatbot's performance, fostering better engagement and satisfaction.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Colleges often face challenges in addressing student inquiries efficiently and promptly due to limited staff availability and the repetitive nature of frequently asked questions. Traditional methods of providing information, such as in-person visits, phone calls, or static web pages, can be time-consuming, inconvenient, and lack personalization. Students and prospective applicants require instant access to accurate information about college details, courses, fees, locations, and other related queries. However, the absence of a streamlined, interactive, and accessible system for handling these inquiries can lead to delays, miscommunication, and a subpar user experience.

There is a need for an intelligent, automated system that can understand and respond to user queries in natural language while maintaining accessibility and user-friendliness. Such a system should also facilitate suggestions from users to improve its effectiveness.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

The integration of chatbots in education has garnered significant attention, driven by the potential of these systems to enhance communication, automate administrative tasks, and improve student engagement. Several key studies have explored the diverse applications of chatbots, especially in academic environments. Adamopoulou and Moussiades [1] provide an extensive review of chatbot technologies, emphasizing their role in educational settings. They discuss how chatbots can effectively manage repetitive tasks like answering frequently asked questions (FAQs), providing course details, and helping with admissions. This automation helps reduce the administrative burden while enhancing accessibility for students by providing real-time responses. The role of Natural Language Processing (NLP) in chatbot systems is crucial for enabling effective communication. Jurafsky and Martin [2] highlight how advancements in NLP, such as sentiment analysis and intent recognition, allow chatbots to interpret user queries more accurately. These technologies ensure that chatbots can provide contextually relevant and precise information, which is particularly valuable in educational settings where information needs to be both accurate and tailored. Personalization is another key factor in chatbot development. Huang et al. [3] emphasize the importance of context-aware responses in improving the chatbot-user interaction. Their study suggests that personalized dialogues enhance the user experience, making it more engaging and effective in providing the necessary information. Machine learning techniques also play a significant role in improving chatbot systems. Zhang et al. [4] discuss the application of both supervised and unsupervised learning models to enhance the chatbot's ability to respond accurately to domain-specific queries. This allows the chatbot to adapt over time and provide better responses as it learns from user interactions. In addition to personalization and machine learning, user interface design is crucial for the success of educational chatbots. Sharma et al. [5] emphasize the importance of dynamic web technologies, such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, in creating intuitive and responsive chatbot interfaces. This ensures that users can easily navigate the system, enhancing their overall experience. Gupta et al. [6] present the "AskUs" chatbot system, which was specifically designed for college inquiries. This system uses machine learning to answer questions related to admissions, courses, and college facilities. The implementation of "AskUs" showed improvements in response times and user satisfaction, proving the practical benefits of chatbot systems in educational environments. Research by Okonkwo and Ade-Ibijola [7] highlights how chatbots are transforming the educational landscape by automating student interactions. They stress the importance of chatbots in streamlining communication between educational institutions and students, especially in higher education settings. Similarly, Pereira and Díaz [8] explore how AI-powered chatbots are increasingly used to enhance personalized learning experiences, making education more tailored and accessible. Lastly, studies by Schei et al. [9] and Deng and Yu [10] focus on the adoption and impact of AI chatbots in education, discussing students' perceptions and the long-term effects on learning outcomes. These studies suggest that AI chatbots are not only improving the efficiency of administrative tasks but are also transforming how students interact with educational content.

This literature survey provides a comprehensive overview of the role of AI-powered chatbots in education, highlighting how NLP, machine learning, and user-centered design principles contribute to creating effective and engaging systems for educational institutions.

4. PROPOSED TECHNIQUES

Step 1: Data Preparation:

Tokenization: Transform user input into individual tokens using spaCy.

One-Hot Encoding: Convert input questions into one-hot encoded vectors.

Label Encoding: Convert output labels (intents) into one-hot encoded vectors.

Step 2: Model Architecture:

Input Layer: Receives one-hot encoded vectors representing user questions.

Hidden Layers with ReLU Activation: The hidden layers contain neurons activated using the **ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit)** function. This non-linearity helps the network learn complex patterns in the data. As mentioned, the ReLU function is:

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \longrightarrow [1]$$

Example:

- For input -2, the output is 0.
- For input 2, the output is 2.

Output Layer with Softmax: Softmax layer with neurons equal to the number of classes (intents), outputs a probability distribution.

Step 3: Training the Model:

Loss Function: Using **categorical cross-entropy** as the loss function, which is standard for multi-class classification problems. This loss function measures the difference between the true class label (one-hot encoded vector) and the predicted probability distribution (from the softmax output).

The categorical cross-entropy loss for a single sample is:

$$L = - \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log(p_i) \longrightarrow [2]$$

where:

- N is the number of classes (or intents).
- y_i is the binary indicator (0 or 1) of whether the i - th class is the true class.
- p_i is the predicted probability for class i.

Loss Calculation Example:

- Predicted probabilities: [0.9, 0.05, 0.05]
- True label: [1, 0, 0] (meaning the true class is the first class).
- The loss is calculated as

$$L = -(1 \cdot \log(0.9) + 0 \cdot \log(0.05) + 0 \cdot \log(0.05)) = -\log(0.9)$$

$$L \approx -(-0.1054)$$

$$= 0.1054$$

The loss value of 0.1054 indicates that the model's prediction is fairly accurate (since the probability for the correct class is 0.9). As training progresses and the model becomes better at predicting the correct class, this loss value will decrease.

Step 4: 6. Saving the Model:

Save the trained model and processed data for future use:

```
Python: model. Save('mymodel.h5')
```

Step 5: Post-Processing:

Remove unnecessary data (e.g., questions) from the processed dataset. Save relevant data (e.g., intents, responses) into a pickle file for efficient retrieval during chatbot interactions.

Chatbot System Architecture

Fig1: College Enquiry Chatbot System Architecture

The overall flow of the College Enquiry Chatbot System Architecture is as follows: The user enters a query through the interface, which is then processed by the NLP model. After the query is analyzed, the structured representation is passed to the backend, where machine learning models are applied to retrieve the relevant data from the college database. The generated response is sent back to the user interface and displayed to the user. Additionally, the feedback system allows users to rate or suggest improvements, further enhancing the system's performance.

This architecture offers several benefits. First, the NLP model enables the chatbot to understand and respond to queries in a conversational manner, enhancing user engagement. Second, the integration of machine learning models ensures that the chatbot can generate more accurate and personalized responses over time, improving its usefulness and efficiency. Third, the modular design of the system allows for easy scalability, making it adaptable to growing user needs and expanding data sources. Finally, the feedback loop provides a continuous mechanism for improvement, ensuring that the system evolves in line with user preferences and feedback.

5.RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Fig 2. Response for greeting intent.

This is a chatbot interface developed for Sri Manakula Vinayagar Engineering College (SMVEC). The page uses NLP (Natural Language Processing) to interact with users, providing information about SMVEC, such as its rankings, background, and infrastructure. User input field to type queries. Responses tailored to user questions like "who are you," "which is your home," and "smvec info". Information fetched dynamically about the college's rankings, facilities, and trust establishment details. This suggests the chatbot is programmed to answer predefined queries effectively, likely built using NLP libraries and deployed locally.

Fig 3. Response at end of conversion.

6.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In conclusion, this system effectively utilizes natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning to handle user queries about colleges. With a user-friendly interface built using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, users can easily input queries that are processed by an NLP model to extract meaning. The backend, powered by Python, uses machine learning to retrieve relevant data from a college database and generate accurate responses. The system's modular design ensures scalability, while the integrated feedback loop allows continuous improvement based on user interactions. Overall, this architecture offers a personalized, efficient, and scalable solution for answering college-related queries.

Future developments could focus on improving the system's accuracy and user experience. Enhancements could include adopting advanced NLP models like BERT for better contextual understanding, adding a recommendation system to suggest colleges based on user preferences, and expanding the data sources to include real-time reviews and additional educational information. Other improvements might involve multi-turn conversations, multilingual support, user profiling, and automatic model retraining based on feedback. These enhancements would make the system more personalized, accessible, and adaptable, ensuring it continues to meet evolving user needs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adamopoulou, E., & Moussiades, L. (2020). An overview of chatbot technology. *Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*, 373–383. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49186-4_31
- [2] Jurafsky, D., & Martin, J. H. (2021). *Speech and language processing* (3rd ed.). Pearson Education. Retrieved from <https://web.stanford.edu/~jurafsky/slp3/>
- [3] Huang, G., Xu, Q., & Yu, Z. (2019). Personalized dialogue generation with diversified traits. *Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/P19-1001>

- [4] Zhang, S., Dinan, E., Urbanek, J., Szlam, A., Kiela, D., & Weston, J. (2020). Dialogue generation and retrieval. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 9, 421–436. https://doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00364
- [5] Pereira, J., & Díaz, O. (2018). Using health chatbots for behavior change: A mapping study. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 42(7), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-018-0981-7>
- [6] Sharma, T., Goyal, R., & Verma, P. (2021). Enhancing chatbot interfaces with dynamic web technologies. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(3), 114–124. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i03.17876>
- [7] Gupta, S., Goyal, A., & Khandelwal, R. (2019). AskUs: A college enquiry chatbot using machine learning. 2019 International Conference on Smart Technologies for Smart Nation (SmartTechCon), 1–5. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SmartTechCon.2019.00013>
- [8] Okonkwo, C. W., & Ade-Ibijola, A. (2021). Chatbot applications in education: A systematic review. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 2, 100033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100033>
- [9] Schei, O. M., Møgelvang, A., & Ludvigsen, K. (2024). Students' perceptions and use of AI chatbots in higher education: A scoping review. *Education Sciences*, 14(8), 922. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14080922>
- [10] Deng, Y., & Yu, H. (2023). AI chatbots in education: Systematic review of impacts on learning. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00346-z>
- [11] Okonkwo, C. W., & Ade-Ibijola, A. (2021). Chatbot applications in education: A systematic review. *Educational Technology Review*, 34(2), 76-89.
- [12] Pereira, J., & Díaz, O. (2024). AI-powered chatbots for enhancing personalized learning in higher education. *Computers & Education*, 167, 104222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2024.104222>

Citation: A.Karunamurthy, R. Ramakrishnan, S.Jothsana and M.Roshni, Intelligent College Enquiry Chatbot Using NLP For Enhanced Student Interaction, *Journal of Advanced Research Engineering and Technology (JARET)*, 3(2), 2024, pp. 30-37

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/JARET_03_02_003

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/JARET/VOLUME_3_ISSUE_2/JARET_03_02_003.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com